

#23

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

TRIZ (THEORY OF INVENTIVE PROBLEM-SOLVING)

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Any stage in the interactive process when new/external knowledge is needed from the outside.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>No limitation on size, but used by smaller projects/initiatives that are seeking new forms of external knowledge (often unexpectedly) that is unavailable in their small group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Technical expertise may need to be developed (e.g. through training) for identifying and using new forms of external knowledge.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the extent of external knowledge sought. This tool is best used with complementary tools in this handbook (Tool#2, Tool#11, Tool#12), which themselves require dedicated time to implement.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>External knowledge, which may or may not be fees-based. Furthermore, this tool is best used with Tool#2, Tool#11, Tool#12, otherwise it can be lengthy to implement.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools #2, 11, 12.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC (OF THE TOOL)

Image source: www.marketing91.com

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Assess (often unexpected) needs for new forms of knowledge in the multi-actor process.
- Assess how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives.
- Engage new forms of external knowledge to a multi-actor group to fuel interactive innovation.
- Address deficit/s in the group's 'knowledge bank' as the interactive innovation process evolves.
- Facilitate actors in the multi-actor group to interrogate new forms of knowledge.

Background and Logic

Other tools in this handbook focus on identifying, leveraging and assessing how different forms of knowledge are used in the interactive innovation process. As the process of interactive innovation evolves and the group becomes aware of new opportunities for innovation, they may require new forms of knowledge that may not have been envisaged when the multi-actor group was formed. Resource-availability and other practical constraints may exist, preventing the inclusion of a partner/actor once the interactive innovation is in progress.

The TRIZ (theory of inventive decision-making) model inspires this tool. TRIZ has been identified as useful for SMEs pursuing sustainability-oriented innovation (SOI), which are often 'dependent on external sources of innovation knowledge' [Feniser et al. \(2017\)](#). TRIZ (as described by [Feniser et al. \(2017\)](#)) is by definition a process where actors in an initiative access technical methods of problem-solving, using TRIZ software, identifying and accessing new forms of knowledge. We present an approach in this tool that is inspired by some characteristics of TRIZ, but does not offer an explanation of the whole approach nor its full utility. More information in relation to TRIZ is accessible [here](#).

We refer to a characteristic of TRIZ by offering a discussion topic guide, led by principles of 'inventive decision-making'. Essentially, the discussion topic guide encourages participants in a multi-actor group to examine challenges and opportunities in different ways and from new perspectives. We then present a tool for groups to use to 'interrogate' new information, facilitating them to take active roles in examining new information through their own (multi-actor) lenses.

Materials

- For online meetings, an online platform such as Klaxoon or Mural can be used in conjunction with an audio function such as Zoom.
- A graphic designer may be commissioned to design a systems map, but this is optional.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.
- This tool may be building on other tools (such as tool#2 that assigns actors to tasks/actions according to their knowledge). If so, the outcomes of those tools (particularly with regard to knowledge held by actors of a group) should be put in place for the workshop to implement this tool.

Step 2: Problem-Driven Process

This tool is employed at any juncture in the interactive innovation process when a challenge/problem arises. It may become apparent to actors that they do not have enough/the required information, expertise or skills to effectively engage with the problem/challenge, to turn it into an opportunity for interactive innovation process.

Once a problem/s or challenge/s arises, this tool can be engaged to facilitate actors assess existing knowledge/skills within the group and to identify more knowledge (in an inventive way) if necessary.

The problem/s are written as topic guides on sheets of flipchart paper.

Step 3: Re/Assessment of Knowledges/Skills

Tool #2 identifies project/initiative tasks and matches them with the different knowledges/skills/interests of members of the multi-actor group. Tool#11 generates hypotheses about tasks/actions in relation to what likely effect they will have. Tool#12 phases actions with an external 'expert'.

The outcomes of Tool#2/Tool#11/Tool#12- often implemented iteratively throughout the innovation process - are revisited using this tool. Do the tasks require revision? Do the hypotheses regarding cause and effect require revision? The revised tasks are updated and replace the preceding ones, as necessary.

Then, the group turns to the question of whether the revised tasks are suitable for any actor/s within the multi-actor group to undertake? If not, the required skill-set (as perceived at this stage of the process) is noted and associated with the task. The facilitator ensures that the discussion of tasks/knowledges is as multi-actor as possible, with ideas generated by as many actors within the group as possible.

The group is then facilitated to examine the problem/challenge through new lenses - entering into the 'inventive decision-making' process. A suite of questions to prompt this inventive decision-making process is outlined below. It is important to note that the questions below may be altered by the facilitator to suit the focus of the tasks/project/initiative; and, importantly, the language of participants in the multi-actor group. Furthermore, not all questions must be used, though it is important for the facilitator to challenge participants. The facilitator can choose/adapt any questions deemed most relevant, including some challenging questions. The aim is to encourage participants in the interactive innovation process to look at challenges/problems with new perspectives. This is the purchase of TRIZ - it can facilitate actors to identify new opportunities in response to challenges/problems, which allows them to identify (in a subsequent step) the appropriate type/range of knowledge/expertise to pursue the opportunities.

On a table/board in the room of the workshop, the flipchart paper (from Step 1, identifying problems/challenges) is hung, and an additional topic guide is written: 'IDEAS'. New ideas (for tasks/actions/problem solving) are written on sticky notes by participants, as they iteratively emerge from the process as the facilitator leads participants through the questionnaires below. The facilitator regularly asks participants if they have any new ideas for responding to the problems/challenges ideas identified, prompted by discussions of the following questionnaires.

Innovative System/Situation Questionnaire

- Name the system and its primary function? (this resonates with Tool# 22 in this handbook, System ID)
- What is the current and desired system structure?
- How does the system execute the primary function now?
- What is the operating environment?
- What are the available resources and natural phenomena?
- What are the problems or opportunities?
- What factor/mechanism constrains achievement?
- Can a substitute problem be solved?
- What system changes are allowed/prohibited?
- What time, money, people issues constrain solutions? Previous attempts? Solved elsewhere?

Source: Adapted from [Apte \(2020\)](#)

Identify the Problem Questionnaire

We begin with “5W’s and an H” of Innovation. Ask these questions of every system so that the system function and problem is identified.

- **W1.** Who has the problem?
- **W2.** What does the problem seem to be? What are the resources?
- **W3.** When does the problem occur? Under what circumstances?
- **W4.** Where does the problem occur?
- **W5.** Why does the problem occur? What is the root cause?
- **H1.** How does the problem occur? How can the problem be solved?

Source: Adapted from [Apte \(2020\)](#)

The output of Step 2 is an assessment of problems/ challenges through new lenses. New ideas for addressing problems/challenges are added to the flipchart paper. They are clustered and, optionally, shortlisted phased using Tool #12.

4. Assessing the need for/Introducing new knowledge

- This step involves introducing new knowledge to the group, if it is required.
- The ideas for revised actions are assessed by the group – does the group have the required knowledge/expertise to implement them?
- If not, the tasks/requiring external knowledge are focused on.
- Considering the social networks of all the actors involved, decisions are reached about who/what assistance to invite into the group (temporarily or on a longer-term basis). Resource issues and implications are discussed. For some groups, complimentary advice and expertise may be available from government agencies and NGOs. For other groups, funding may be sought to bring the required knowledge/expertise to the group, by adding a new partner. The types of options available to different groups are identified in other LIAISON resources, such as PLA manual and practice abstracts on co-learning produced by WP2, how-to guides produced by WP7.
- For short interventions from external actors, such as guest seminars or workshops, the following tool can be used to facilitate group members to interrogate/internalise new knowledge from the external actor/s. The terminology/language to the ‘Interview technique’ below can be adapted to suit the multi-actor group context/the particular topic/interests of the group. The example below is customised to the topic of ‘farm partnerships’ and a peer-to-peer group of farmers who wish to learn more about farm partnerships.

Interview Technique

The Interview Technique is an effective tool for farmers to learn from other farmers' experiences. It provides an alternative to farmers giving formal presentations or talks to the Farm Partnership Incubation Group on one hand and to loose, unstructured discussions on the other. A strategic approach can be taken to highlight the diversity of benefits associated with Farm Partnerships. It is necessary to highlight the diversity of benefits identified by research on Irish farmers' experiences of Farm Partnerships because they are relevant in different ways to members of the Farm Partnership Incubation Group who have different circumstances, needs, preferences and aspirations.

The Interview Technique is instrumental for such a strategic approach and involves the facilitator interviewing farmers who are selected because of the diversity of benefits they have experienced and the associated diversity of their circumstances, needs, preferences and aspirations. Members of the Farm Partnership Incubation Group are the audience of this 'live' interview. The facilitator asks questions that prompt the farmers being interviewed to elaborate important contextual information in relation to various challenges they were experiencing and the way in which solutions were found through a Farm Partnership. The key benefits of Farm Partnerships are highlighted in this way, providing a focused introduction to an open discussion and questions from the audience.

Interview Technique

The interview is a presentation in which one or more resource people (i.e. farmers with experience of Farm Partnerships) respond to questioning by one or more interviewers.

The interview may be used...

1. To explore a specific topic in depth where a more formal presentation is not desired by either resource expert or audience.

Some Advantages

1. The presentation is less formal than a speech or lecture
2. The audience is represented by the interviewer, which saves time and can be an efficient way of targeting key topics of interest
3. There is some assurance that the discussion will follow the interests of the members of the audience, as the interviewer asks questions that directly reflect the interests and objectives of the group.
4. Many resource people shy away from formal presentation and may not be willing to invest the required preparation time. The Interview Technique delegates some responsibility to the interviewer and provides a more relaxed method for the resource person to impart their knowledge and experiences
5. For the audience, listening to an interview can be far more engaging than listening to a formal presentation. Enhanced learning is possible in this context.

Some Limitations

1. The role of the audience is basically passive
2. The effectiveness of the technique is reliant on interviewer being strategic in terms of achieving the objectives of the audience and his/her adeptness at managing a lively, interesting and relevant interview.

Physical Requirements

1. Adequate seating so every member of the audience may see and hear the speakers in comfort
2. Use of a platform/microphone where necessary

Procedure

1. The interviewer and resource person discuss the overall topic and agree on the general line of questioning
2. The interviewer asks the resource person questions designed to explore various aspects of the topic and improvises questions as the interview progresses.
3. Open discussion and questions from the audience may be used at the end of the interview.

Source: Adapted from Fuhrman and Rohs (2011)

